

Minor Constituents of *Lantana camara*

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Early work on *Lantana camara* Roxb., Verbenaceae reported¹⁻³ the isolation of triterpenoids, flavonoids and verbascosides. This paper describes the isolation of a new triterpene acid (1) which occurs as a minor constituent in *L. camara*.

Exhaustive chromatography of the CHCl₃ extract of the air-dried roots of the plant yielded in addition to hederagenin and 19-hydroxyursolic acid, a small amount of a new triterpene acid (1), C₃₀H₄₆O₄. It formed a methyl ester (2) upon methylation and a monoacetate (3) upon acetylation. The ¹H nmr spectrum of 1 showed resonances for only six tertiary C-methyl groups of the olean-12-ene skeleton, a pair of doublets of doublets at δ 2.48 (*J* 15.0, 7.0, 4.0 Hz) and 2.55 (*J* 15.0, 10.5, 7.0 Hz) assignable to ketomethylene protons at C₂ assuming the keto group at C₃. An AB system (δ 3.46 and 3.98, *J* 11.6 Hz) attributed to nonequivalent hydroxymethylene protons which shifted downfield (δ 3.90 and 4.60) upon acetylation, indicates the presence of a primary OH group at C-25. The signal at δ 5.35 gave evidence of the presence of a trisubstituted double bond. The mass spectrum of 1 showed diagnostically important peaks which are consistent with the fragmentation pattern characteristic for Δ¹²-pentacyclic triterpenes⁶. It is also evident from the mass spectral fragments that the keto and OH groups are located in A/B ring while COOH group in C, D or E rings. The ready loss of COOH group from *m/z* 248 to give an ion peak at *m/z* 203 indicates the presence of COOH group at C-17. The location of keto group at C-3 is highly probable on biogenetic ground. One of the carbons C-23, C-24, C-25 or C-26 might be in the form of hydroxymethyl. Positions C-23 and C-24 were ruled out because both 23-hydroxy-3-oxoolean-12-en-28-oic acid⁷ and 24-hydroxy-3-oxoolean-12-en-28-oic acid¹ unlike 1, undergo retro-aldolisation in the presence of alkali. A supporting evidence for the placement of keto

group at C-3 and primary OH group at C-25 was gained by the treatment of compound 1 with concentrated H₂SO₄ to yield lantanolic acid³ (4) (identified by comparison of physical and spectral data). The foregoing evidence lead to the assignment of a tentative structure for compound 1 as 25-hydroxy-3-oxoolean-12-en-28-oic acid which might be expected as an important biogenetic intermediate during the biosynthesis of compounds having hemiacetal linkage in the plant. However, this reports the isolation of this compound for the first time from the nature.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. ¹H nmr (90 and 300 MHz, TMS as internal standard), EIMS (70 eV) and ir (KBr) spectra were recorded. Silica gel (60-120 mesh, Glindia's) was used for tlc and cc and the spot on tlc was visualised by spraying Liebermann-Burchardt reagent.

Lantana camara roots were collected during February to March 1992 in Varanasi (a voucher specimen preserved). The air-dried powdered roots (4.0 kg) were extracted with CHCl₃ and the extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to give brown residue (200 g). A portion of the extract was chromatographed on a Si-gel column (eluted with EtOAc) to yield triterpene acid (1), m.p. 276-80°. (Found: C, 76.8; H, 10.0. C₃₀H₄₆O₄ requires: C, 76.5; H, 9.9%); *v*_{max} KBr 3 450 (OH), 1 710, 1 685 (C=O); *m/z* 470 M⁺ (46), 440 (44), 426 (58), 396 (24), 248 (100, base peak), 203 (80), 133 (8); δ (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) 0.78 (3H, s), 0.91 (3H, s), 0.94 (3H, s), 1.17 (3H, s), 1.30 (3H, s), 2.48 (1H, ddd, *J* 15.0, 7.0, 4.0, H-2eq), 2.55 (1H, ddd, *J* 15.0, 10.5, 7.0, H-2ax), 2.82 and 2.88 (1H, dd, H-18), 3.46 and 3.98 (1H each, AB doublets, *J* 11.6 Hz, H-25), 5.35 (1H, t, *J* 2.9 Hz, H-12).

Methyl ester (2): Compound 1 was treated with ethereal CH₂N₂ at room temperature for 24 h and the product was purified by cc and crystallised from MeOH as colourless crystals, m.p. 208-09°; *v*_{max} 3 400, 1 725, 1 710; *m/z* 484 M⁺ (57), 454 (95), 395 (37), 394 (42), 262 (75), 248 (12), 203 (100, base peak), 133 (27); δ (CDCl₃, 90 MHz) 0.76 (3H, s), 0.93 (3H, s), 0.96 (3H, s), 0.98 (3H, s), 1.17 (3H, s), 1.29 (3H, s), 2.46 (2H, m, H-2), 2.76 and 2.90 (1H, dd, H-18), 3.66 (3H, COOMe), 3.46 and 4.06 (1H each, AB doublets, *J* 11.6 Hz, H-25), 5.26 (1H, t, H-12).

Acetate (3): Compound 1 was treated with a mixture of Ac₂O-pyridine at room temperature for 48 h and the reaction medium evaporated under reduced pressure to give

- 1: R = OH, R¹ = H
2: R = OH, R¹ = CH₃
3: R = OAc, R¹ = H

the product and crystallised from MeOH as colourless flasks, m.p. 228–30°; δ (CDCl₃, 90 MHz) 0.80 (3H, s), 0.91 (3H, s), 0.96 (3H, s), 1.19 (3H, s), 1.21 (3H, s), 1.28 (3H, s), 2.38 (2H, m, H-2), 2.08 (3H, s, O-CO-CH₃), 2.76 and 2.88 (1H, dd, H-18), 3.90 and 4.60 (1H each, AB doublet, J 11.6 Hz, H-25), 5.24 (1H, t, H-12).

Conversion of 1 to 3,25-epoxy-3- α -hydroxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid (4): Compound 1 was treated with concentrated H₂SO₄ in C₆H₆ under reflux for 4 h, then cooled to room temperature and left for 24 h. The solid thus obtained was washed with water, dried and crystallised from MeOH as white crystals, m.p. > 300°, which was identified as 3,25-epoxy-3- α -hydroxyolean-12-en-28-oic acid by comparison of physical and spectral data with that reported in literature³.

The latter EtOAc fraction was rechromatographed with CHCl₃ : MeOH mixture to give 19-hydroxyursolic acid⁸ and hederagenin⁹ which were identified by comparison of physical and spectral data (ir, nmr and mass) with that reported in literature. This is the first report of the isolation of 19-hydroxyursolic acid and hederagenin from the genus *Lantana*.

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